

NDAC/LO/044
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SUBROUTINES FOR CALCULATING PROPER DIRECTION

by L Lindegren

A subroutine package 'proper.f' has been written, by which the proper direction of a star or planet is calculated. It consists of 9 subprograms arranged as follows:

No reference is made to external routines or files, except that geocentric orbital data for the satellite are supposed to be available in a special disk file 'satorb'. (A separate program generating test data on such a file is also available.) The procedure is invoked through the statement

```
CALL proper(T, opar, u, ierr)
```

in which T is the time in seconds from J1988.0 TDT, opar(1:20) is a double-precision array of object parameters (see below), and u(1:3) a DP array in which the proper direction with respect to $\underline{N}$ is returned. The error flag (ierr) becomes negative if T is outside the permitted range; normal return is ierr = 0.

A very brief description of the subprograms used by subroutine proper is given below. For details, see program listings at the end of this note.

- SUBROUTINE sun : calculates the barycentric position of the Sun ($\underline{b}_S$) at the given time T (see Lindegren, 1984 June 15)
- SUBROUTINE earth : calculates the barycentric position and velocity of the Earth ($\underline{b}_E, \dot{\underline{b}}_E$) at the given time T (see Lindegren, 1984 June 8)
- SUBROUTINE geosat : calculates the geocentric position and velocity of the satellite (observer), $\underline{g}_O$ and $\dot{\underline{g}}_O$, at the given time T. Fourier coefficients etc for these are read from the disk file 'satorb'.
- SUBROUTINE codirp : calculates the coordinate direction ($\underline{u}$) to a planet at time T, given object parameters in opar()
- SUBROUTINE codirs : calculates the coordinate direction ($\underline{u}$) to a star at time T from object parameters in opar()
- SUBROUTINE natdir : calculates the natural direction ($\hat{\underline{u}}$) of the object by applying gravitational deflexion by the Sun and Earth to the coordinate direction
- SUBROUTINE prpdir : calculates the proper direction ($\underline{u}$) of the object by Lorentz transformation to the proper frame
- FUNCTION fourie : calculates the sum of a Fourier series

The array of object parameters, opar(1:20), is an attempt to summarize the state of knowledge on any particular object, stellar or planetary, in a standardized form suitable for rapid calculations. The length of this array (20) and the precise contents of it, as described below, are only preliminary. Concerning the parameters for planetary objects (asteroids), it should be remembered that a given planet is formally regarded as a different object, with its own ID number, for each time it enters the FOV. Provisionally, it is furthermore assumed that planetary objects are given ID numbers in excess of 90,000,000, while stellar objects have ID numbers below this limit.

Contents of the object parameters array opar(i), i = 1 to 20

i	opar(i) [stellar object]	opar(i) [planetary object]
1	object ID number ($< 9 \cdot 10^7$)	object ID number ($> 9 \cdot 10^7$)
2	reference epoch (T_o) [s]	reference epoch (T_o) [s]
3	$\cos \alpha_o$ (α_o = barycentric R.A. at T_o)	x-component of $\bar{u}$ at T_o
4	$\sin \alpha_o$	y-component of $\bar{u}$ at T_o
5	$\cos \delta_o$ (δ_o = barycentric Dec. at T_o)	z-component of $\bar{u}$ at T_o
6	$\sin \delta_o$	$\dot{x}$ -component of $\dot{\bar{u}}$ at T_o [s^{-1}]
7	$\mu_\alpha \cos \delta_o$ [rad s^{-1}]	$\dot{y}$ -component of $\dot{\bar{u}}$ at T_o [s^{-1}]
8	μ_δ [rad s^{-1}]	$\dot{z}$ -component of $\dot{\bar{u}}$ at T_o [s^{-1}]
9	Π [rad]	p = inverse distance at T_o [m^{-1}]
10	ρ = radial velocity [m s^{-1}]	$\dot{p}$ = derivative of p [$m^{-1} s^{-1}$]
11	$\Delta\alpha \cos \delta_o$ [rad]	(TBD)
12	$\Delta\delta$ [rad]	(TBD)
13-18	(TBD)	(TBD)
19	$H = \frac{1}{2}(B + V)$ [mag]	$H = \frac{1}{2}(B + V)$ at T_o [mag]
20	B-V [mag]	B-V [mag]

NOTE: opar(13) - (20) are not used in the present subroutines.

The circumstance that a planetary object 'exists' for only the 20 seconds or so it takes to travel across the FOV means that its coordinate direction and inverse distance (which are the quantities needed to calculate the natural direction) are adequately represented by $\underline{u}(T_0)$, $\dot{\underline{u}}(T_0)$, $p(T_0)$, and $\dot{p}(T_0)$, where T_0 = reference epoch such that $|T - T_0| \lesssim 10$ s, and p = inverse distance. It is assumed that a special procedure (yet to be written) will recognize a planet the first time it is observed in a certain FOV crossing, assign its ID number, compute the object parameters for the entire crossing, and incorporate these with the current object catalogue. This could be done immediately prior to the IDT Preprocessing.

In writing the present subroutines, special care was taken in order to get the basic transformations in a form which is both rigorous and computationally efficient. It was also assumed that successive calls are usually made with T within the same 12^h interval (say), or even with exactly the same T for several objects observed in the same frame. Thus, the calculation of ephemeris data ($\underline{b}_S$, $\underline{b}_E$, $\dot{\underline{b}}_E$, $\underline{g}_0$, $\dot{\underline{g}}_0$) is automatically suppressed if these were already obtained in the last call (with the same T). This is quite important, as it turns out that subroutine 'earth' is by far the most time-consuming part of the calculation:

<u>Subroutine called by 'proper'</u>	<u>Execution time [ms] on HP9000</u>
sun	0.5
earth	36.2
geosat (provided 'satorb' need not be referenced)	6.8
codirs, codirp	0.9 (star), 0.1 (planet)
natdir	1.4 (star), 2.5 (planet)
prpdir	1.2
<hr/>	
total for 'proper', same T:	3.6 (star), 3.9 (planet)
new T:	47.6 (star), 48.1 (planet)

With about 4 objects per frame, the average execution time would be some 15 ms per object.

If necessary, the execution time for calculating the Earth ephemeris could be brought down to about 2.3 ms, by using a Chebyshev representation (degree = 8, maximum error about 1 m and 1 mm/s) on each 10 day interval. Subroutines for calculating the Chebyshev coefficients and evaluating the polynomials exist on our computer.

```

*****
SUBROUTINE  proper(T, opar,      u, ierr)
*****
c
c  HIPPARCOS - NDAC - General routines - Proper direction
c
c  Calculates the proper direction to an object at a given time;
c  using a set of 'object parameters' contained in the array  opar().
c
c  Input:
c  T              - time from J1988.0 TDT                      [s]
c  opar(1)        - object ID number
c                  < 9d7  for a stellar object
c                  > 9d7  for a planetary object
c  opar(2)        - reference epoch (TD)                        [s]
c  opar(i), i=3-18 - these are different for stars and
c                  planets; see SUBROUTINE  codirs  and
c                  codirp ; respectively; for explanation
c  opar(19)       - H-magnitude of object
c  opar(20)       - B-V colour index
c
c  Output:
c  u(i), i=1-3   - proper direction to object
c  ierr          = 0  on normal return
c                < 0  on error condition:
c                  ierr = -DCBA, where
c                  A = 1  if error in SUBROUTINE  sun
c                  B = 1  if error in SUBROUTINE  earth
c                  C = 1  if error in SUBROUTINE  geosat
c                  D = 1  if error in SUBROUTINE  codirp
c
c  Execution time per call (HP9000):
c  48  ms  if T is not the same as on previous call
c  3.6 ms (star)  if T has not been changed since the last call
c  3.9 ms (planet)  - " -
c
c  L Lindegren  1984 July 26
c
c  IMPLICIT DOUBLE PRECISION (a-h,o-z)
c  DIMENSION  opar(20), u(3), uco(3), unat(3)
c  DIMENSION  be(3), bedot(3), bo(3), bodot(3), bs(3), go(3),
c  ,          godot(3), ho(3)
c  SAVE  Tprev, bo, bodot, go, ho
c  DATA  Tprev/-1d8/
c
c  If this is the first call with the present value of T, then
c  calculate and save:  bo()   = barycentric position of observer
c                      bodot() = barycentric velocity of observer
c                      go()    = geocentric position of observer
c                      ho()    = heliocentric position of observer
c
c
c  IF (T .NE. Tprev) THEN
c    CALL  sun(T,      bs,          ierr1)
c    CALL  earth(T,   be, bedot,  ierr2)
c    CALL  geosat(T, go, godot,  ierr3)
c    DO 100  i = 1, 3
c      bo(i)   = be(i)   + go(i)
c      bodot(i) = bedot(i) + godot(i)
c      ho(i)   = bo(i)   - bs(i)
c 100  CONTINUE
c      Tprev = T
c  ENDIF

```

SUBROUTINE proper, ct'd

```
c
c To calculate the coordinate direction, use codirp for a planet,
c                                     codirs for a star
c
  IF (opar(1) .GT. 9d7) THEN
    CALL codirp(T, opar,          uco, p, ierr4)
  ELSE
    CALL codirs(T, opar, bo,     uco, p)
  ENDIF
c
c Calculate natural direction unat() :
c
  CALL natdir(uco, p, ho, go,    unat)
c
c Calculate proper direction u() :
c
  CALL prpdir(unat, bodot,      u)
c
  ierr = ierr1 + 10*(ierr2 + 10*(ierr3 + 10*ierr4))
c
  RETURN
  END
```

```

c*****
c      SUBROUTINE geosat(T,      go, godot, ierr)
c*****
c
c  HIPPARCOS - NDAC - General routines - Satellite ephemeris
c
c  Calculates the geocentric equatorial position and velocity of the
c  satellite at a given time.
c
c  Orbital parameters for contiguous time intervals (of some 12h)
c  are supposed to be available in the file 'satorb'.
c
c  Input:
c    T      = time in seconds from J1988.0 (12h TDT)
c
c  Output:
c    go(i)  = geocentric rectangular equatorial coordinates [m]
c    godot(i) = geocentric equatorial velocity components [m/s]
c    ierr   = 0 on normal return, -1 if T is outside the range
c            defined by 'satorb'
c
c  NOTE: This routine is in a very preliminary shape
c
c  Execution time:   6.8 ms if T is in same interval as on prev. call
c                  1000 ms if T is random among 100 intervals
c
c  L. Lindegren  1984 July 24
c
c      IMPLICIT DOUBLE PRECISION (a-h,o-z)
c      DIMENSION go(3), godot(3), p(64)
c      SAVE p, irec
c      DATA p/0d0, -1d0, 62*0d0/, irec/0/
c 1 CONTINUE
c      IF ((p(1) .LE. T) .AND. (T .LE. p(2))) THEN
c
c  T is in an interval for which the parameters have been saved from
c  a previous call:
c
c          DT = T - p(3)
c          f = DT*p(4)
c          DO 100 j = 1, 3
c              i0 = 10*j-4
c              go(j) = p(i0) + p(i0-1)*DT
c                  + fourie(f, 4, p(i0+1), p(i0+5))
c              i1 = i0+30
c              godot(j) = p(i1) + p(i1-1)*DT
c                  + fourie(f, 4, p(i1+1), p(i1+5))
c 100 CONTINUE
c          ierr = 0
c      ELSE

```

SUBROUTINE geosat, ct'd

```

c
c T is not in the same interval as on previous call;
c search file 'satorb' for orbital parameters of relevant interval
c
      lu = 10
      OPEN(UNIT=lu, FILE='satorb', ACCESS='DIRECT', RECL=8*64)
199      CONTINUE
      irec0 = irec
200      CONTINUE
      irec = irec + 1
      READ(UNIT=lu, REC=irec, ERR=299) p
      IF ((T .LT. p(1)) .OR. (T .GT. p(2))) GOTO 200
      CLOSE(UNIT=lu)
      GOTO 1
299      CONTINUE
      IF (irec0 .NE. 0) THEN
          irec = 0
          GOTO 199
      ELSE
          ierr = -1
          irec0 = 0
          DO 210 i = 1, 3
              go(i) = 0d0
              godot(i) = 0d0
210          CONTINUE
          CLOSE(UNIT=lu)
      ENDIF
      ENDIF
c
      RETURN
      END

```

```

c*****
c      SUBROUTINE  codirp(T, opar,      uco, p, ierr)
c*****
c
c  HIPPARCOS - NDAC - General routines - Coordinate direction to planet
c
c  Calculates the coordinate direction to a planet at a given time
c
c  Input:
c    T          - time from J1988.0 TDT                      [s]
c    opar(1)    - object ID number (> 9d7 for a planet)
c    opar(2)    - reference epoch (T0)                      [s]
c    opar(3)-(5) - coordinate direction at T0
c    opar(6)-(8) - derivative of coordinate direction      [1/s]
c    opar(9)    - inverse distance at T0                   [m]
c    opar(10)   - derivative of inverse distance          [1/m/s]
c    opar(11)-(20) - (not used by this subroutine)
c
c  Output:
c    uco(i), i=1-3 - coordinate direction at time T
c    p              - inverse distance at time T            [1/m]
c    ierr          = 0 on normal return, -1 if abs(T-T0) > 100 s
c
c  Execution time per call (HP9000): 0.13 ms
c
c  L Lindegren 1984 July 26
c
c      IMPLICIT DOUBLE PRECISION (a-h,o-z)
c      DIMENSION  opar(20), uco(3)
c
c      d = T - opar(2)
c      uco(1) = opar(3) + d*opar(6)
c      uco(2) = opar(4) + d*opar(7)
c      uco(3) = opar(5) + d*opar(8)
c      p      = opar(9) + d*opar(10)
c
c      ierr = 0
c      IF (dabs(d) .GT. 1d2)  ierr = -1
c
c
c      RETURN
c      END

```

```

c*****
c      SUBROUTINE codirs(T, opar, bo, uco, p)
c*****
c
c  HIPPARCOS - NDAC - General routines - Coordinate direction to a star
c
c  Calculates the coordinate direction towards a star at a given time
c  from its astrometric parameters and the observer's barycentric
c  coordinates.
c
c  Input:
c    T          - time from J1988.0 TDT                      [s]
c    opar(1)    - object ID number ( < 9d7 for a star)
c    opar(2)    - reference epoch (T0)                        [s]
c    opar(3)    - cos(RAD), RAD = barycentric R.A. at T0
c    opar(4)    - sin(RAD)
c    opar(5)    - cos(Dec0), Dec0 = barycentric Dec. at T0
c    opar(6)    - sin(Dec0)
c    opar(7)    - p.m. in R.A., times cos(Dec0)              [rad/s]
c    opar(8)    - p.m. in Dec.                               [rad/s]
c    opar(9)    - parallax                                    [rad]
c    opar(10)   - radial velocity                             [m/s]
c    opar(11)   - correction in R.A., times cos(Dec0)       [rad]
c    opar(12)   - correction in Dec.                         [rad]
c    opar(13)-(20) - (not used by this subroutine)
c    bo(i), i=1-3 - barycentric coordinates of observer     [m]
c
c  Output:
c    uco(i), i=1-3 - coordinate direction
c    p             - inverse distance ( = 0)
c
c  Execution time per call (HP9000): 0.93 ms
c
c  L Lindegren 1984 July 26
c
c  IMPLICIT DOUBLE PRECISION (a-h,o-z)
c  DIMENSION opar(20), bo(3), uco(3)
c  PARAMETER (au = 1.49597870d11)
c
c  d = T - opar(2)
c  p = opar(9)/au
c  q = 1d0 + d*p*opar(10)
c
c  da = opar(11) + d*opar(7)
c  dd = opar(12) + d*opar(8)
c
c  uco(1) = q*opar(5)*opar(3)-da*opar(4)-dd*opar(6)*opar(3)-p*bo(1)
c  uco(2) = q*opar(5)*opar(4)+da*opar(3)-dd*opar(6)*opar(4)-p*bo(2)
c  uco(3) = q*opar(6)
c                                     +dd*opar(5)
c                                     -p*bo(3)
c
c  unorm = 1d0/dsqrt(uco(1)**2 + uco(2)**2 + uco(3)**2)
c
c  uco(1) = unorm*uco(1)
c  uco(2) = unorm*uco(2)
c  uco(3) = unorm*uco(3)
c
c  p = 0d0
c
c  RETURN
c  END

```

```

*****
SUBROUTINE natdir(uco, p, ho, go, unat)
*****
C
C HIPPARCOS - NDAC - General routines - Gravitational deflexion
C
C Calculates the natural direction to an object by applying gravi-
C tational deflexion by the Sun and Earth. The object may be at
C a finite distance (p > 0).
C
C Source: Vectorial Astrometry, (2.5.5) (modified)
C
C Input:
C   uco(i), i=1,2,3 - coordinate direction to object
C   p           - inverse distance to object [1/m].
C               p may be set = 0 for non-Solar System
C               objects, with some saving in computing time.
C   ho(i), i=1,2,3 - heliocentric coordinate of observer [m]
C   go(i), i=1,2,3 - geocentric coordinate of observer [m]
C
C Output:
C   unat(i), i=1,2,3 - natural direction to object
C
C Execution time per call (HP9000):  1.4 ms with p = 0
C                                   2.5 ms with p > 0
C
C
C L Lindegren 1984 July 25
C
C   IMPLICIT DOUBLE PRECISION (a-h,o-z)
C   DIMENSION uco(3), ho(3), go(3), unat(3)
C   PARAMETER (c = 299792458d0, c2 = c*c,
C             , GS = 1.32712438d20, GE = 3.986005d14,
C             , s = 2d0*GS/c2, e = 2d0*GE/c2)
C
C   h = dsqrt(ho(1)**2 + ho(2)**2 + ho(3)**2)
C   g = dsqrt(go(1)**2 + go(2)**2 + go(3)**2)
C
C (p = 0) for a star, (p > 0) for a planet:
C
C   IF (p .LE. 0d0) THEN
C     qh = h
C     qg = g
C   ELSE
C     qh = h*(h*p+dsqrt((uco(1)+ho(1)*p)**2+(uco(2)+ho(2)*p)**2 +
C                     (uco(3)+ho(3)*p)**2))
C     qg = g*(g*p+dsqrt((uco(1)+go(1)*p)**2+(uco(2)+go(2)*p)**2 +
C                     (uco(3)+go(3)*p)**2))
C   ENDIF
C
C   as = s/(h*(qh + uco(1)*ho(1) + uco(2)*ho(2) + uco(3)*ho(3)))
C   ae = e/(g*(qg + uco(1)*go(1) + uco(2)*go(2) + uco(3)*go(3)))
C
C   d1 = ho(1)*as + go(1)*ae
C   d2 = ho(2)*as + go(2)*ae
C   d3 = ho(3)*as + go(3)*ae
C
C   ad = 1d0 - uco(1)*d1 - uco(2)*d2 - uco(3)*d3
C
C   unat(1) = uco(1)*ad + d1
C   unat(2) = uco(2)*ad + d2
C   unat(3) = uco(3)*ad + d3
C
C RETURN
C END

```

```

c*****
c      SUBROUTINE  prpdir(unat, v,      u)
c*****
c
c  HIPPARCOS - NDAC - General routines - Stellar aberration
c
c  Calculates the proper direction to an object by applying stellar
c  aberration (Lorentz transformation).
c
c  Source: Vectorial Astrometry, (2.5.8) (modified)
c
c  Input:
c    unat(i), i=1,2,3  - natural direction to object
c    v(i),     i=1,2,3  - velocity of observer [m/s]
c
c  Output:
c    u(i),     i=1,2,3  - proper direction to object
c
c  Execution time per call (HP9000):  1.2 ms
c
c
c  L Lindegren  1984 July 25
c
c      IMPLICIT DOUBLE PRECISION (a-h,o-z)
c      DIMENSION  unat(3), v(3), u(3)
c      PARAMETER (c = 299792458d0, c2 = c*c)
c
c      e = dsqrt(c2 - v(1)**2 - v(2)**2 - v(3)**2)
c      f = (1d0 + (unat(1)*v(1)+unat(2)*v(2)+unat(3)*v(3))/(c+e))/e
c
c      u(1) = unat(1) + f*v(1)
c      u(2) = unat(2) + f*v(2)
c      u(3) = unat(3) + f*v(3)
c
c      unorm = 1d0/dsqrt(u(1)**2 + u(2)**2 + u(3)**2)
c
c      u(1) = unorm*u(1)
c      u(2) = unorm*u(2)
c      u(3) = unorm*u(3)
c
c      RETURN
c      END

```

```

c*****
c      DOUBLE PRECISION FUNCTION fourie(x, n, a, b)
c*****
c
c  HIPPARCOS - NDAC - General routines - Fourier series
c
c  Evaluates the Fourier series
c
c      fourie = a(1)*cos(x) + a(2)*cos(2*x) + ... + a(n)*cos(n*x) +
c              + b(1)*sin(x) + b(2)*sin(2*x) + ... + b(n)*sin(n*x)
c
c  using Clenshaw's algorithm.
c
c  Restriction:  0 <= n <= 20    (NO CHECK IS MADE!)
c
c  Execution time:  approx  0.74 + 0.075*n  ms per call
c
c  L Lindegren  1984 July 23
c
c      IMPLICIT DOUBLE PRECISION (a-h,o-z)
c      DIMENSION  c(22), s(22), a(n), b(n)
c      y = dcos(x)
c      z = 2d0*y
c      k2 = n + 2
c      k1 = n + 1
c      c(k2) = 0d0
c      s(k2) = 0d0
c      c(k1) = 0d0
c      s(k1) = 0d0
c      DO 100  k = n, 1, -1
c          c(k) = z*c(k1) - c(k2) + a(k)
c          s(k) = z*s(k1) - s(k2) + b(k)
c          k2 = k2 - 1
c          k1 = k1 - 1
c 100 CONTINUE
c
c      fourie = y*c(1) - c(2) + s(1)*dsin(x)
c
c      RETURN
c      END

```